

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

KINETICS OF OXIDATION OF FAST GREEN FCF DYE WITH 1-CHLOROBENZOTRIAZOLE IN ALKALINE MEDIUM: MECHANISTIC AND SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDY

Prema Kadappa Reddy, Fathyah Omar, Asha Iyengar*

Yuvaraja's College, University of Mysore, Mysuru 570005, Karnataka, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 31/01/2017

Available online

28/02/2017

Keywords

Oxidation,
Fast Green FCF (FGF),
1-Chlorobenzotriazole,
Benzotriazole.

ABSTRACT

Fast Green FCF (FGF) is a synthetic food dye. The kinetics of oxidation of Fast Green FCF with 1-chlorobenzotriazole in NaOH medium has been spectrophotometrically investigated at λ_{\max} 625 nm at the temperature 301 K. The reaction exhibited a pseudo -first order dependence of the rate on [FGF], first order dependence on the rate of [CBT]₀, fractional order dependence on [OH⁻]. And inverse fractional order on addition of reduced product [BTA]. It fails to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile under the experimental conditions employed. Thermodynamic parameters for the reaction have been evaluated. Effects of dielectric constant and ionic strength of the medium on the reaction rate have also been studied. Oxidation products are identified and characterized by LC-MS. A probable reaction scheme is proposed and an appropriate rate law is deduced to account for the observed kinetic data.

*Corresponding Author

Dr. T. Asha Iyengar

Associate Professor

Department of Chemistry,

Yuvaraja's College Mysore,

University of Mysore.Mysuru-570005

asha.iyengarycm@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Asha Iyengar** et al. Kinetics of Oxidation of Fast Green FCF Dye with 1-Chlorobenzotriazole in Alkaline Medium: Mechanistic and Spectrophotometric Study. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(02).

Copy right © 2017 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Fast green dye has been widely used in histology and cytology. It has been found to have tumorigenic effects in experimental animal as well as mutagenic effects in both experimental animals and humans. Furthermore, in its undiluted form it poses a risk of irritation to eyes, skin, digestive tract and respiratory tract. The heterocyclic dye fast green FCF (Scheme 1) is used in dyeing, printing, leather processing, fluorescent pigments and widely used as a colorant in the cosmetics and drug industries. The direct release of wastewater containing fast green FCF causes serious environmental problems due to its dark color and toxicity [1].

Scheme 1. Molecular structure of Fast Green FCF dye.

Fast Green FCF (FGF) is a triarylmethane food dye which is widely used as food colorant in tinned green peas and other vegetables, jellies, sauces, dishes made of fishes, desserts and dry bakery items (FCF in the name of dye refers to *For Coloring Food*). It is a substitute of Light Green SF Yellowish in histology, as its color is less likely to fade [2]. It is used as a protein stain in the electrophoresis. The extensive use of this dye induces carcinogenic effects [3] as it produces sarcomas at the site of repeated subcutaneous injection and causes eye, skin and upper respiratory tract irritation. It is an immunotoxic agent and inhibits the release of neurotransmitter [4,5]. The applications and proven toxicity of FGF render it necessary to develop a sensitive, fast and reliable approach to determine FGF in pharmaceutical, food and biological samples. Owing to concerns over the analytical determination of the dye, several methods have been developed for the analysis of FGF employing variable techniques. A review of the literature reveals that the detection of the FGF dye has been reported using high performance liquid chromatography [6,7], liquid chromatography-electro spray tandem mass spectroscopy [8], CPE scanometry [9], capillary electrophoresis [10] and spectrofluorimetry [11] were reported. However most of these techniques often suffer from some unfavorable conditions such as high cost and complex sample preparation due to tedious analytical steps. Moreover, lengthy analysis time is required which make these techniques practically not helpful in routine analysis. Therefore in recent times, spectrophotometric methods have attracted the attention of researchers because of their sensitivity in the determination of organic molecules, rapidity of analysis, inexpensive and no complex sample pretreatment methods.

Traditional removal techniques such as coagulation/flocculation, membrane separation (ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis) or adsorption by activated carbon are based only on a phase transfer of the pollutant. Recently, advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) have been developed to oxidize the organic compound into CO_2 , H_2O and inorganic ions, or into biodegradable compounds [12]. These environmentally friendly AOPs are considered as promising wastewater treatment methods. This article reporting the spectrophotometric method of removal of toxicity of FGF using a new oxidant 1-CBT. Although there are no reports on the kinetics of oxidation of FGF in the literature. Several studies on the degradation, photodegradation and electrooxidation of FGF have been reported by a few researchers [13-16].

1-Chlorobenzotriazole (CBT) is a versatile oxidizing agent and its solution chemistry is reasonably well understood [17]. 1-CBT is an N-halogen compound that contains cyclic three nitrogen chain. It has the capacity to undergo certain chemical reactions which prove its usefulness in organic syntheses. It is soluble in water, chloroform, dichloromethane and ethyl acetate. 1-CBT can be used as a reagent for oxidation and chlorination reactions. Recently, 1-CBT, has attracted the attention of organic chemists as a novel organic reagent in organic syntheses because of its reactivity towards a number of functional groups[23]. 1-CBT has considerable potential as an oxidant; it oxidizes alcohols to carbonyl compounds, hydrazo- to azo-compounds and 1, 1-disubstituted hydrazine, all in high yield under very mild conditions. There are few reports on the kinetics of oxidation of some organic compounds by 1-CBT [18-22]. But there are no reports on the kinetics of oxidation of FGF by 1-CBT. With this background, the present study reports the results pertaining to the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of FGF by 1-CBT in alkaline medium. Kinetics of oxidation of FGF by 1-CBT in acidic medium was also studied in our laboratory and the reaction was found to be very slow but in alkaline medium is moderate and measurable.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Experimental

1-CBT Solution

1-CBT was prepared by the method of Johnson et al [24]. An aqueous solution of 1-CBT was prepared, standardized periodically by the iodometric method and preserved in an amber colored bottle for further use [25].

Fast Green Solution

As the substrate, FGF, is prone light degradation, aqueous solutions of FGF (SD. Fine. Ltd) were freshly prepared and used immediately. Fast green (ethyl-[4-[4-[ethyl-(3-sulpho- phenyl)methyl]amino]phenyl]-(4-hydroxy-2 -sulphophenyl)methylidene]-1-cyclohexa-2,5 -dienylidene)-[(3-sulphophenyl)methyl]azani- um). Fast green is also known as food green 3, FD & C green No. 3, green 1724, solid green FCF, (C. I. 42053) [26]. Its molecular formula is $C_{37}H_{34}N_2O_{10}S_3Na_2$, and its molar mass is 808.85 g/mol. Stock solution of FGF was prepared in volumetric flask with doubly distilled water.

The other chemicals NaOH, Methanol, $NaClO_4$ and NaCl of required concentration was prepared with distilled water and stored as stock solutions.

Kinetic Procedure

Kinetic runs were prepared under pseudo-first order conditions of $[FGF] \ll [CBT]$ at 301 K. For each run requisite amount of solutions of FGF solution was taken in a stoppered pyrex glass tube whose outer surface was coated black to eliminate photochemical effects. A required amount of distilled water was added to maintain a constant volume in all runs. The tube was thermally equilibrated at a given temperature. The reaction was initiated by adding a measured amount of pre-equilibrated CBT solution and shaken periodically for uniform concentration. The progress of the reaction was monitored using UV-VIS. Spectrophotometer LMSP-UV1200 by measuring the absorbance of FGF at its λ_{max} of 625 nm at regular intervals of three half-lives. The pseudo-first-order rate constants k were calculated. Regression analysis of the experimental data was carried out on a WINDOWS 2007 intel core i5 computer to obtain the regression coefficient, R^2 .

RESULTS

Effect of CBT and FGF concentration on the reaction rate.

Under pseudo -first order conditions of $[CBT]_0 > [FGF]_0$ at constant temperature the absorbance of the reaction mixture at regular time interval 't' was recorded and the plots of $\log(2 + \log \text{Abs})$ versus time were linear indicating a first order dependence of the reaction rate on $[FGF]$. (Table 1, Figure 1). The pseudo -first order rate constant k obtained at 301 K were found to be independent of $[FGF]_0$. The rate of the reaction on varying concentration of $[FGF]$, $[CBT]$ and $[NaOH]$ at constant temperature 301 K are tabulated in Table 2. Furthermore, a plot of $\log k$ versus $\log [CBT]_0$ was straight line with a slope 1.07 showing first order dependence on $[CBT]$ (Table 2, Figure 2, $R^2=0.998$).

Table 1: FGF=2x10⁻⁵ M CBT=10x10⁻⁴ M NaOH = 10x10⁻³ M; λ_{max} = 625 nm and Temp 301 K.

Time (mins)	absorbance	2 + log (abs)
0	1.2468	2.095
4	1.1754	2.070
8	1.1228	2.050
12	1.0781	2.032
16	1.0341	2.014
20	0.9885	1.994
24	0.9483	1.976
28	0.9057	1.956
32	0.8703	1.939
36	0.8433	1.925
40	0.8168	1.912
44	0.7952	1.900
48	0.7728	1.888
52	0.7584	1.879
56	0.7411	1.869
60	0.7124	1.852

Figure 1:

Table 2: Effect of varying concentration of [FGF], [CBT], [NaOH] on the reaction rate $\lambda_{\max} = 625 \text{ nm}$ and temp 301 K.

[FGF] $\times 10^5 \text{ M}$	[CBT] $\times 10^4 \text{ M}$	[NaOH] $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$k \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.0	10.0	10.0	1.83
1.2	10.0	10.0	1.84
1.4	10.0	10.0	1.84
1.6	10.0	10.0	1.87
1.8	10.0	10.0	1.85
2.0	10.0	10.0	1.86
2.2	10.0	10.0	1.86
2.4	10.0	10.0	1.88
2.0	20.0	10.0	3.69
2.0	30.0	10.0	5.97
2.0	40.0	10.0	8.10
2.0	50.0	10.0	9.90
2.0	60.0	10.0	13.03
2.0	10.0	20.0	2.50
2.0	10.0	30.0	3.04
2.0	10.0	40.0	3.62
2.0	10.0	50.0	4.15

Figure 2: Effect of [CBT].

Effect of [NaOH] on the reaction rate.

The reaction rate increased with increasing the concentration of NaOH (Table 2, figure 3, $R^2=0.992$). A plot of $\log k$ versus $\log [\text{OH}^-]$ was straight line with a positive slope of 0.5 showing fractional order dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$.

Figure 3: Effect of [OH⁻].

Effect of reduction product [BTA] on the reaction rate.

The effect on the rate due to the addition of reduced product BTA of 1-CBT to the reaction mixture as other conditions maintained constant was studied in the range - 2×10^{-3} to 8×10^{-3} M of BTA. The reaction rate was found to be retarded. A plot of $\log k$ versus $\log [BTA]$ was a straight line with a negative slope of 0.33 showing inverse fractional order. (Table 3, Figure 3, $R^2=0.970$).

Table 3: Effect of varying Benzotriazole (BTA) Concentration on the Reaction Rate.

[FGF]= 2×10^{-5} M; [CBT]= 10×10^{-4} ; [NaOH] = 10×10^{-3} M; λ_{\max} = 625 nm and temp 301 K.

[BTA] x 10 ³ (M)	k x 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)
0.0	1.86
2.0	1.64
4.0	1.30
6.0	1.05
8.0	0.94

Figure 4: Effect [BTA].

Effect of Dielectric constant (D) on the reaction rate.

The effect of dielectric constant (D) on the reaction rate was studied by varying MeOH content (0-30%) at constant experimental conditions. The rate decreased with an increase in MeOH content of the medium. The plot of $\log k$ versus $1/D$ gave a straight line with a negative slope. (Table 4, Figure 5, $R^2=0.93$). This effect is in conformity with the Amis concept of dipole-dipole interaction or dipole-ion interaction[27].

Table 4: Effect of varying Methanol Concentration on the Reaction Rate.

[FGF]= 2×10^{-5} M ; [CBT]= 10×10^{-4} ; [NaOH] = 10×10^{-3} M ; λ_{\max} = 625 nm and temp 301 K

MeOH (%)	Dielectric Constant (D)	$k \times 10^4 (s^{-1})$	1/D	4+log k
0	76.73	1.86	0.0130	0.27
10	72.37	1.81	0.0138	0.258
20	67.48	1.73	0.0148	0.239
30	62.71	1.67	0.0159	0.225

Figure 5: Effect of Methanol.**Effect of halide ion and ionic strength on the Reaction Rate.**

Addition of halide ion (0.4×10^{-3} to 4×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}) in the form of NaCl to the reaction mixture had no effect on the rate. Ionic strength of the reaction medium varied by adding NaClO₄ (0.001 to 0.1 mol dm^{-3}) also did not affect the rate.

Effect of temperature on the react ion rate.

Kinetic runs were performed at various temperatures in the range 301 K to 317K while keeping other experimental conditions the same. An Arrhenius plot of log k versus 1/T (Table 4, $R^2=0.986$) was used to calculate the activation parameters, namely energy of activation (E_a), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger). These results are shown in Table 5, Figure 6. The value of ΔH^\ddagger indicates that the reactions are enthalpy controlled. The more positive values of ΔG^\ddagger points out a highly solvated transition state. The negative values of ΔS^\ddagger signifies that the transition state is more rigid than the initial state with less degrees of freedom. The values of frequency factor (log A) specify the frequency of collisions and orientation of the reaction molecules.

Table 5: Effect of temperature on the reaction rate.

FGF= 2×10^{-5} M CBT= 10×10^{-4} M NaOH = 10×10^{-3} M; λ_{\max} = 625 nm and Temp 301 K

Temp in K	$k \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$	Activation Parameters
301	1.86	E_a : 68.89 KJ/mol
305	1.91	ΔH^\ddagger : 66.38 KJ/mol
309	1.96	ΔS^\ddagger : -95.74 J/K/mol
313	2.06	ΔG^\ddagger : 37.57 KJ/mol
317	2.13	log A : 8.22

Figure 6: Effect of Temperature.

Reaction Stoichiometry

Varying ratios of the oxidant (1-CBT) to FGF in alkaline medium were equilibrated at 301 K for 24 hrs. Aliquots of the reaction mixture were idometrically titrated with standard thiosulphate solution, using starch indicator, to determine the concentration of unchanged 1-CBT. The mole ratio (number of moles of CBT consumed per mole of FGF) was calculated. The results of FGF reaction with CBT showed a definite stoichiometry of 1: 1 (scheme 2).

Scheme 2:

Product Analysis

The reaction mixture in the stoichiometric ratio was allowed to progress for 48 h in presence of alkaline medium at 301 K under stirred conditions. After completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC), the reaction products were extracted with ethyl acetate. The oxidation products were confirmed by LC-MS analysis. The oxidation product of FGF are sodium 3-hydroxybenzenesulfonate and sodium 3-(2-(3-(4-((3-((chlorooxy)sulfonyl)benzyl)(ethyl)amino)benzoyl)phenyl)butyl)benzenesulfonate. The mass spectra showed a molecular ion peak at 665 and 197 amu, clearly confirming the benzene sulfonate derivatives as the oxidized products. The reduction product of CBT, benzotriazole (BTA) was isolated and identified by TLC using butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:1 v/v) as solvent and iodine as the detecting agent ($R_f=0.92$). The obtained R_f value was consistent with literature value.[28]. It was also noticed that there was no further reaction of these oxidation products under the present set of experimental conditions.

Molecular Weight: 196.16

Molecular Weight: 664.16

Figure 7: The mass spectra which showed a molecular ion peak at 197 amu and 665 amu indicating the structure of oxidized product as benzene sulfonate derivative.

Mechanism

The probable mechanism is proposed below, based on the experimental results obtained.

Step 1:

Step 2:

Scheme 3.

DISCUSSION

1-CBT being N-haloamine gives several oxidizing species in aqueous solution. The concentration of each species depends on the concentration of 1-CBT and on the nature (polar or non-polar) and pH of the medium. Benzotriazole (BTA), the parent compound of CBT, has pK_b 5.8 and hence it might largely exist in protonated form in an aqueous solution [28]. The prominent species present in alkaline halamine solutions are RNCl (CBT), HOCl and OCl^- oxidizing species. One could expect appreciable concentrations of HOCl and OCl^- as oxidizing species. The retardation of the reaction rate by the presence of benzotriazole indirectly supports the possibility of involvement of HOCl as an oxidizing species during the reaction. The following reaction mechanism appears plausible to account for proposed the rate law.

A first order dependence on $[\text{CBT}]$ ($R^2 = 0.998$) and fractional order dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$ ($R^2 = 0.992$) and fractional order on $[\text{OH}^-]$ ($R^2 = 0.992$) observed retardation of rate by BTA can be explained by the following mechanism:

The total effective concentration of CBT can be written as

$$[\text{CBT}]_t = [\text{BTA}] + [\text{HOCl}] + [\text{X}]$$

Scheme 4:

$$\text{Rate} = k_3 [\text{X}]$$

$$\text{Assuming } [\text{CBT}]_t = [\text{CBT}] + [\text{HOCl}] + [\text{X}] \quad \dots(1)$$

$$k_1 = \frac{[\text{BTA}][\text{HOCl}]}{[\text{CBT}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots(2)$$

$$[\text{CBT}] = \frac{[\text{BTA}][\text{HOCl}]}{k_1 [\text{OH}^-]} \quad \dots(3)$$

$$k_2 = \frac{[\text{S}][\text{HOCl}]}{[\text{X}]} \quad \dots(4)$$

$$[\text{HOCl}] = \frac{[\text{X}]}{k_2 [\text{S}]} \quad \dots(5)$$

Substitute $[\text{CBT}]$ and $[\text{HOCl}]$ in $[\text{CBT}]_t$

$$[\text{CBT}]_t = \frac{[\text{BTA}][\text{HOCl}]}{k_1 [\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{[\text{X}]}{k_2 [\text{S}]} + [\text{X}]$$

$$[\text{CBT}]_t = \frac{[\text{BTA}][\text{X}]}{k_1 [\text{OH}^-] k_2 [\text{S}]} + \frac{[\text{X}]}{k_2 [\text{S}]} + [\text{X}]$$

$$[\text{CBT}]_t = [\text{X}] \left\{ \frac{[\text{BTA}] + k_1 [\text{OH}^-]}{k_1 [\text{OH}^-] k_2 [\text{S}]} + 1 \right\}$$

$$[\text{X}] = \frac{[\text{CBT}]_t k_1 [\text{OH}^-] k_2 [\text{S}]}{k_1 [\text{OH}^-] + [\text{BTA}]} + 1 \quad \dots(6)$$

Substitute $[\text{X}]$ in $\text{Rate} = k_3 [\text{X}]$

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{CBT}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{CBT}]_t [\text{OH}^-] [\text{S}]}{k_1 [\text{OH}^-] + [\text{BTA}]} + 1 \quad \dots(7)$$

The rate law (7) is in close agreement with the experimental results obtained which indicated first order with respect to [FGF] and [CBT] and fractional order in [OH⁻] and inverse fractional order for [BTA]. The addition of acrylamide to the reaction mixture had no effect on the reaction rate. This shows the absence of free radicals in the reacting system during oxidation. The change in the ionic strength of the medium during the oxidation reaction by using NaClO₄ did not alter the rate, indicating that non-ionic species involved in the rate determining step. A slight negative dielectric constant effect on the rate supports the dipole-dipole interaction in the rate determining step. The proposed mechanism is supported by the moderate values of energy of activation and other thermodynamic parameters. The fairly high positive values of free energy of activation and enthalpy of activation indicate that the transition state is highly solvated, while the high negative entropy of activation suggests the formation of compact activated complex with fewer degrees of freedom.

CONCLUSION

Fast Green FCF dye is commonly used as additives in food, medicines and soft drinks to get suitable and natural looking colors, because of their high brightness, stability, low cost and wide ranges of shades. Consequently, they have become common industrial and environmental pollutants during their synthesis and applications. Some of the artificial coloring ingredients are toxic to our health and environmentally hazardous. There were not many reports on the kinetics of oxidation of FGF dye with organic oxidants in the literature. Hence the present work was undertaken and reports the spectrophotometric method of kinetics of oxidation and removal of toxicity of FGF using a new oxidant 1-CBT.

RECOMMENDED FUTURE RESEARCH

Ruthenium Chloride catalyzed kinetics of oxidation Fast Green FCF with 1-CBT in presence of acidic medium carrying out. The oxidation of structurally similar dyes of Fast Green FCF will be carrying out.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

One of the authors, Prema greatly acknowledges with gratitude the support and encouragement of the Management of Teresian College, Mysuru and also thanks Prof.R .A. Vasantha, H.O.D, Department of Chemistry, Teresian College Mysuru and Dr. Raghavendra for their valuable suggestions regarding the reaction mechanism.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

FGF : Fast Green FCF
 CBT : Chlorobenzotriazole
 BTA : Benzotriazole

REFERENCES

1. M.A. Ali, S.A. Bashier, Food Add. Contam. 23 (2006) 452
2. W. Au, and T. Hsu, Environ. Mol. Mutagen. 1 (1979) 27.
3. M. Ali, and S. Bashier, Food Addit. Contam. 23 (2006) 452.
4. J. P. Brown, G. W. Roehm, and R. J. Brown, Mutat. Res. 56 (1978) 249.
5. J. Van Hoof, Neurosci. Lett. 318 (2002) 163.
6. N. Vachirapatama, J. Mahajaroensir, and W. Visessanguan, J. Food. Drug. Anal. 16 (2008) 77.
7. N. Yoshioka, and K. Ichihashi, Talanta 74 (2008) 1408.
8. F. Feng, Y. Zhao, W. Yong, L. Sun, G. Jiang, and X. Chu, J. Chromatogr. B 879 (2011) 1813.
9. A. Shokrollahi, and T. Roozestan, Anal. Method. 5 (2013) 4824.
10. K. Fraige, N. Antonio, R. Pinto, and E. Carrilho, J. Liq. Chromatogr. R. T. 32 (2009) 1862.
11. D. Dalavi, A. Kamble, D. Bhopate, P. Mahajan, G. Kolekar, and S. Patil, RSC Adv. 5 (2015) 69371
12. R.F.P. Nogueira, M.R.A Silva, A.G. Trovó, Solar Energy 79 (2005) 384.
13. A. Kumar, M. Paliwal, R. Ameta and S.C. Ameta*, J. Iran. Chem. Soc., Vol. 5, No. 2, June 2008, pp. 346-351.
14. Gargi Sharma, Dipti soni, Surbhi Aenjamin, Rakshit Ameta and Sanyogita Sharma' Sci. Revs. Chem. Commun.: 4(4), 2014, 138-145.
15. Indu Bhati, Pinki B. Punjabi, Suresh C. Ameta, Maced.J. Chem and chem. Eng. Vol 29, No.2,pp.195-2029(2010).
16. Deepti S. Nayak and Nagaraj P. Shetti, Anal. Bioanal. Electrochem., Vol. 8, No.1, 2016, 38-50.
17. R.C.Hiremath, S.M. Mayanna and N. Venkatasubramanian, J. Sci. Ind. Res. 49 122 (1990).
18. R.C Hiremath, R V Jagadeesh, Puttaswamy and S.M Mayanna J. Chem. Sci., Vol. 117, no. 4, pp. 333–336 (2005).
19. N. Nanda, S. M Mayanna and N.M. M Gowda -, Int. J. Chem. Kinet, 31 153 (1990).
20. N. Nanda and S.M. Mayanna, Oxid. Commun. 22 107 (1990).
21. N.Nanda, B.S.Sheshadri and S.M. Mayanna, React. Kinet. Catal. 67 35 (1990)
22. C. Channe Gowda and S. M. Mayanna, Tokmru Vol. 38, No. 12, pp. 1427-1430, (1991).
23. K. Srinivas, M. Vijayashree, and P. V. S. Rao, Ind. J. Chem., 21A, 773 (1982).
24. S. P. Jonnalagadda, R. H. Simoyi, and G. K. Muthakia, J. Chem. Soc. Perkin Trans. II, 1111 (1988).

25. Puttaswamy, D. S. Mahadevappa, and K. S. Rangappa, Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn., 62, 3343 (1989).
26. Fast Green FCF, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fast_Green_FCF, accessed February, 2010.
27. E.S.Amis-Solvent effects on reaction rates and mechanism. Van Nostrand reinhold New York, 257(1970).
28. N. S Srinivasan and Venkatasubramanian N - Tetrahedron Lett. 30 419 (1974).

Submit your next manuscript to **IAJPR** and take advantage of:

Convenient online manuscript submission

Access Online first

Double blind peer review policy

International recognition

No space constraints or color figure charges

Immediate publication on acceptance

Inclusion in **ScopeMed** and other full-text repositories

Redistributing your research freely

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com

